

AUDITORS AND VARIABILITY IN INTEGRATED REPORTING GRAVITY

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Abstract: *This study investigates the link between auditors and variability in integrated reporting gravity for a sample of 134 publicly traded main board firms from the Nigerian Exchange. Auditors' characteristics considered are auditors' opinion, auditors' independence, audit firm size, auditors' tenure, audit quality (big4), and auditors' rotation. In contrast to prior literature, integrated reporting is defined as the index of human capital, financial capital, intellectual capital, social capital, manufactured capital, and natural capital rather than in aggregate dummy terms (if reports are integrated 1, otherwise 0). Further, the analysis examines the association between auditors' characteristics and each of the firm's human capital, financial capital, intellectual capital, social capital, manufactured capital, and natural capital, respectively. Finally, the study analyzes the effects of auditors' characteristics on integrated reporting conjointly. Comparable to general findings from studies that use data outside Nigeria, the empirical analysis as a whole did not discern consistent significant link between the six auditors' characteristics and corporate integrated reporting across the 134 firms. However, three auditors' characteristics are found to influence corporate integrated reporting gravity in isolated cases. Overall, results provide evidence that even under emerging market, the role of auditors vary across firms. Consequently, these findings do not lend support to the notion that uniform auditors characteristics should be mandated. This study suffers from some limitations. First, the study sample is limited to only 1,340 observations. However, this is due to collecting the data manually and to the small number of listed firms on the Nigerian Exchange. Second, the study period begins in 2013 and ended in 2022, which last for 10 years only. Third, although this study examines the effect of auditors' characteristics, not all the auditors' features have been examined in our models. Nonetheless, this research is pioneering in analysing the effects of auditors' characteristics on integrated reporting and as far as we know no existing research has examined the link between them.*

Keywords: *audit firm size, audit quality, auditors' independence, auditors' opinion, auditors' tenure, financial capital, human capital, integrated reporting, intellectual capital, manufactured capital, natural capital, Nigeria, social capital*

Introduction

Integrated reporting (IR) is a new area of research interest or concern in accounting and finance. Despite the proposed benefits to stakeholders and the number of contributions aimed at identifying best practices in its adoption, IR is still scarcely absorbed among companies in Nigeria and where it is adopted, the structure is not fully implemented. The development in reporting has started with corporate social responsibility reporting, in which the emphasis is on how the activities of a firm affect its host communities (Bouten et al., 2011; Dawkins & Ngunjiri, 2008; de Villiers & Alexander, 2014; Lungu et al., 2011; Marquis & Qian, 2014; Noronha et al., 2013; Perrini, 2005; Reynolds & Yuthas, 2008; Shabana et al., 2017; Tanko & Yahaya, 2005; Thompson & Zakaria, 2004; Yahaya & Apochi, 2021; Yahaya & Lamido, 2022; Yusuf et al., 2020). It migrated to environmental reporting, in which, the concern is about the effects of a firm's operations on the environment (Adams, 2004; Ahmad et al., 2003; Awen & Yahaya, 2023; Azzone et al., 1997; Brophy & Starkey, 2016; Clarkson et al., 2011; Cormier & Gordon, 2001; Cormier & Magnan, 2003; Davis-Walling & Batterman, 1997; Guthrie & Abeysekera, 2006; Sahay, 2004; Yahaya, 2018).

It further advanced to sustainability reporting, which is an attempt to disclose both financial and non-financial reports (Adams & Frost, 2008; Antonia Garcia-Benau et al., 2013; Aras & Crowther, 2009; Dienes et al., 2016; Hahn & Kühnen, 2013; Kolk, 2003; Kolk, 2004; Lozano, 2011; Maclaren, 1996; Siew, 2015; Simnett et al., 2009; Torelli et al., 2020; Umar et al., 2021; Usman & Yahaya, 2023; Yahaya & Alkasim, 2021; Yahaya et al., 2022). In recent times, the focus of research has shifted to integrated reporting (Abeysekera, 2013; Adams, 2015; Busco et al., 2013; de Villiers et al., 2014; de Villiers & Hsiao, 2017; Dumay et al., 2016; Eccles & Krzus, 2010; García-Sánchez et al., 2013; Onyabe et al., 2016; Stubbs & Higgins, 2014; Vaz et al., 2016; Yahaya & Onyabe, 2022).

Integrated reporting has been severally and differently linked in a number of empirical studies. However, these empirical studies have failed to link it with external auditors' characteristics, bearing in mind the roles of auditors in corporate reporting. These roles include, but not limited to evaluating financial reports and assessing accounts for accuracy and compliance; investigating internal systems and operations; assessing risk management approaches; performing audits for other departments, as needed. To fill this gap is the focus of this paper, which is to examine the role of external auditors in corporate integrated reporting, specifically, in an emerging market such as Nigeria. While IR is not mandated in Nigeria as at the time of writing this paper, a number of corporations have adopted it because of the benefits it offer.

IR enhances the way organizations think, plan, and report the story of their business. Many organizations use as an opportunity to communicate a clear, concise, integrated story that explains how value is created within these organizations. IR is an approach that helps businesses think holistically about their strategy and plans, make informed decisions, manage key opportunities and risks to build investor and stakeholder confidence, and help manage the organization's performance. Organizations of all sizes can use to build understanding and trust in their business. As a business owner or manager, securing your customers', suppliers', finance providers', and

other external stakeholders' trust is paramount. Trust in the business is built by succinctly highlighting what drives value. Understanding value creation is enabled by what is called integrated thinking, a central theme of IR, which is based on breaking down internal silos between people and departments so that the organization can collectively better understand the key elements of the business. This includes the governance, strategy, business model, and opportunities and risks in the context of trends and issues affecting the business. Integrated thinking also involves an organization considering the different resources consumed, and the relationships it relies on, leaving it in a better position to make decisions that help ensure its viability and resilience over time.

Despite these benefits, few corporations in Nigeria have adopted IR framework for their reporting. There is need, therefore, to interrogate how integrated reporting could possibly be improved in Nigeria. In this paper, that role falls on the external auditors. The external auditor (henceforth refers to as the auditor). An external auditor is a public accountant who conducts audits, reviews, and other work for clients. An external auditor is independent of all clients, and so is in a good position to make an impartial evaluation of the financial statements and systems of internal controls of those clients. External auditors conduct independent assessments of organizations' financial statements and disclosures. They confirm that financial statements do not contain errors. Companies hire external auditors to ensure financial statements and disclosures remain free of material misstatement. This paper uses six auditors' characteristics as proxies: auditors' opinion, audit firm size, auditors' tenure, audit quality (big4), auditors' independence and auditors' rotation.

This paper is significant to regulators, market players, shareholders, and boards of directors, management, lenders, and a number of other stakeholders. It offers empirical evidence for both policy improvement, performance improvement, future research and it provides additional body of knowledge. In terms of scope, the data is obtained from 2013 to 2022. The variables are limited to six auditors' characteristics and six measures of integrated capitals for IR. The remainder of the paper is organized into four sections. Section 2 presents literature review, covering both conceptual, theoretical and empirical literature. Section 3 presents the research methodology, covering research design, population and sample, sources and methods of data collection, analyses and post estimations diagnostics. Section 4 presents the descriptive statistics, results of diagnostics, correlation matrix and regression results. Section 5 presents the conclusions, drawn based on the empirical results and offers both policy and performance improvement recommendations.

Literature Review

Generally, the majority of empirical studies examining IR have not link it with auditors' characteristics. The few studies on IR are not on the role of external auditors in IR. It is because of this empirical gap that this paper seek to analyze the association between external auditors' characteristics and IR. For example, Sierra-Garcia et al. (2013) study why companies are producing integrated reporting. Based on 7144 worldwide observations, this study identifies the determinants of integrated reporting through a logistic regression model. Their results point out that the likelihood of disclosing an integrated report is positively associated with having the corporate social responsibility report assured, year, size and supplement industry. Still in 2013, Abeysekera outlines the concept of integrated reporting and to propose a template for integrated

reporting in organisations. The study concludes that the integrated report should explain the story of reaching the organisation's vision, underpinned by its values, enacted by management, monitored by governance, and using facets of resources relating to financial capital, intellectual capital, social capital, and environmental capital.

Furthermore, de Villiers et al. (2014) draw insights from accounting and accountability research into the rapidly emerging field of integrated reporting and proposes a comprehensive agenda for future research in this area. The paper shows that the rapid development of integrated reporting policy, and early developments of practice, present theoretical and empirical challenges because of the different ways in which integrated reporting is understood and enacted within institutions. Also, Stubbs and Higgins (2014) investigate the internal mechanisms employed by early adopters of integrated reporting in Australia to manage their reporting process and explores whether integrated reporting is stimulating innovative disclosure mechanisms. Finding show that while the organisations that are producing some form of integrated report are changing their processes and structures, or at least talking about it, their adoption of integrated reporting has not necessarily stimulated new innovations in disclosure mechanisms.

In 2015, Owen reviews the development and their implications in IR and concludes if widely adopted, will require significant developments in professional and university accounting curricula. Also, Serafeim (2015) examines the association between IR and clientele and concludes that integrated reporting is a relatively new phenomenon in the world of corporate reporting that has gained significant momentum in the last ten years. Velte and Stawinoga (2017) evaluate 44 empirical studies on IR which were published especially after the adoption of the IR framework by the International Integrated Reporting Council in December 2013. They show which factors contribute to IR implementation and IR quality. Still in 2017, Lai et al. (2017) show how the principle of materiality gets implemented in integrated reporting (IR) contexts. Drawing on an interpretation of materiality as a social construction, this study explores the meaning that practitioners attach to the principle during their implementation of it. They conclude that the materiality determination process is governed by a specific IR hub. Still in 2017, Dumay et al. (2017) draw insights from contemporary accounting research into integrated reporting as a general concept and IR as espoused by the IIRC. The authors specifically focus on possible barriers and emphasise the specific issues the authors feel could be rectified to advance the IR, along with the areas that may potentially hinder its wider adoption and implementation. The authors see forces, both external and internal, driving IR adoption.

Pistoni et al. (2018) assess the quality of integrated reports issued by firms. They develop a scoring model and an IR Scoreboard, which was applied to analyze 116 integrated reports issued in years 2013 and 2014. The main findings show that IR quality is low. Furthermore, Yahaya and Onyabe (2022) delve into the ways in which audit committee qualities affect integrated reporting of 75 companies outside the financial sector that were traded on the Nigerian Exchange Group. According to the results, the companies' integrated reports successfully fulfilled 70% of all criteria. The quality of integrated reports was also positively impacted by the audit committee's knowledge and meetings. Onyabe et al. (2023) look into the influence of CEO on integrated reporting among 36 African listed communication services companies for 2012-2021. The findings suggest that

CEO ownership negatively affects integrated reporting while CEO tenure, education, age, and compensation positively affect integrated reporting. In addition, CEO gender and the number of owners were found to be immaterial. Based on the varying angles of these studies, the following hypotheses are formulated and tested in this paper:

H₁: Auditors' opinion has no significant effect on IR.

H₂: Audit firm size has no significant effect on IR.

H₃: Auditors' independence has no significant effect on IR.

H₄: Audit quality (big4) has no significant effect on IR.

H₅: Auditors' tenure has no significant effect on IR.

H₆: Auditors' rotation has no significant effect on IR.

Methodology

The Nigerian Exchange (NGX) 134 listed main board founding firms constitute the population and sample of the study. The firms represent about 86 percent of all listed firms on the NGX (134/156). The data for our analysis is sourced from the NGX. We examine the effect of auditors' characteristics on variability in IR gravity using the following model, derived from the existing literature:

$$IR_{i,t} = \alpha + \beta_1 AO_{i,t} + \beta_2 AFS_{i,t} + \beta_3 AT_{i,t} + \beta_4 AI_{i,t} + \beta_5 AQ_{i,t} + \beta_6 AR_{i,t} + \varepsilon_{i,t} \dots (1)$$

$$HC_{i,t} = \alpha + \beta_1 AO_{i,t} + \beta_2 AFS_{i,t} + \beta_3 AT_{i,t} + \beta_4 AI_{i,t} + \beta_5 AQ_{i,t} + \beta_6 AR_{i,t} + \varepsilon_{i,t} \dots (2)$$

$$FC_{i,t} = \alpha + \beta_1 AO_{i,t} + \beta_2 AFS_{i,t} + \beta_3 AT_{i,t} + \beta_4 AI_{i,t} + \beta_5 AQ_{i,t} + \beta_6 AR_{i,t} + \varepsilon_{i,t} \dots (3)$$

$$IC_{i,t} = \alpha + \beta_1 AO_{i,t} + \beta_2 AFS_{i,t} + \beta_3 AT_{i,t} + \beta_4 AI_{i,t} + \beta_5 AQ_{i,t} + \beta_6 AR_{i,t} + \varepsilon_{i,t} \dots (4)$$

$$SC_{i,t} = \alpha + \beta_1 AO_{i,t} + \beta_2 AFS_{i,t} + \beta_3 AT_{i,t} + \beta_4 AI_{i,t} + \beta_5 AQ_{i,t} + \beta_6 AR_{i,t} + \varepsilon_{i,t} \dots (5)$$

$$MC_{i,t} = \alpha + \beta_1 AO_{i,t} + \beta_2 AFS_{i,t} + \beta_3 AT_{i,t} + \beta_4 AI_{i,t} + \beta_5 AQ_{i,t} + \beta_6 AR_{i,t} + \varepsilon_{i,t} \dots (6)$$

$$NC_{i,t} = \alpha + \beta_1 AO_{i,t} + \beta_2 AFS_{i,t} + \beta_3 AT_{i,t} + \beta_4 AI_{i,t} + \beta_5 AQ_{i,t} + \beta_6 AR_{i,t} + \varepsilon_{i,t} \dots (7)$$

Whereas:

IR = Integrated reporting, derived as an index from the six reporting capitals (human, financial, intellectual, social, manufactured and natural capitals).

HC = Human capital, measured as number of staff.

FC = Financial capital, measured as equity to total asset ratio.

IC = Intellectual capital, measured as lease agreement intensity.

SC = Social capital, community investment ratio.

MC = Manufactured capital, measured as plant and machinery intensity.

NC = Natural capital, measured as land and building intensity.

AO = Auditors' opinion, measured as dummy where "1" is assigned to external auditor place a qualified opinion statement or modified it going concern opinion on the audit report and "0" otherwise.

AFS = Audit firm size, measured by log of audit fees

AT = Auditors' tenure, measured as dummy where is computed as "1" is assigned to auditors that have stayed for 3 years and "0" for auditors with less than 3 years of engagement.

AI = Auditors' independence, measured as audit fee divided by revenue (%).

AQ = Audit quality, measured as dummy where "1" is assigned to auditors that member of PWC, Deloitte, E&Y and KPMG as external auditors and "0" otherwise.

AR = Auditors' rotation, measured as dummy where "1" is assigned to auditors that was changed in a particular year and "0" otherwise.

α = Constant
 β_{1-6} = Beta coefficients
i = Firm script (*i* = 134 firms)
t = Time script (*t* = 10 years)
 ε = Idiosyncratic error term

Two (2) control variables, firm size and firm leverage were initially added to the models. However, they models show evidence of specification errors and therefore they were removed. Furthermore, consistent with the previous literature, we use the six capitals as a measure of IR. IR is calculated as the *absolute value of index* derived from human capital, financial capital, intellectual capital, social capital, manufactured capital and natural capital. As in the literature, we consider the absolute measure of the six capitals as a proxy for the extent of integrated reporting. Therefore, high absolute value of the six capitals indicate high IR. In order to analyze the role of external auditors in IR adoption, we use six auditors' characteristics: auditors' opinion, audit firm size, auditors' tenure, auditors' independence, audit quality (big4) and auditors' rotation. It is instructive to note that adoption of IR can potentially have both positive and negative effects. However, as per our stated hypotheses, we predict that there is no significant relationship between auditors' characteristics and IR. Although, we are investigating how adoption of IR can be influenced by the external auditors' characteristics, there are other firm level factors that can influence adoption of IR and which require to be controlled for in the estimations. On the basis of model specification error test, we decide to remove all the control variables in this study.

4. Empirical Results and Discussions

As mentioned in methodology section, our sample consists of the 134 main board founding firms that trade in the NGX, accounting for about 86 percent of all listed firms in Nigeria. Summary of variables of interest are presented in Table 1.

Table 1

Summary Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
IR	1,340	.079	.005	.071	.092
FC	1,340	72.225	25.736	51.54	247.85
IC	1,340	3.196	7.65	0	38.11
HC	1,340	4.08	6.647	0	39.35
SC	1,340	.017	.023	0	.08
MC	1,340	6.957	8.417	.02	44.83
NC	1,340	10.152	8.534	.02	34.19
AO	1,340	.033	.18	0	1
AI	1,340	.576	.056	0	.697
AFS	1,340	4.327	.437	2.683	5.795
AT	1,340	.694	.462	0	1
AQ	1,340	.878	.328	0	1
AR	1,340	.117	.322	0	1

Source: STATA 16 Outputs

From Table 1, the number of observations is 1,340, which is made up of product of 134 firms over 10 years period. Also, the central mean of IR is .079 points, with a standard deviation of .005 points, a minimum and maximum means of .071 and .092, respectively. The standard deviation is lower than the mean suggesting that IR is not yet a mandatory adoption issue in Nigeria. On the component parts of IR, FC averages 72.225 points, with a standard deviation of 25.736 points, and a minimum and maximum means of 51.54 and 247.85, respectively. Again, the standard deviation is lower than the central mean, thus, suggesting that FC is not volatile. In the case of IC, the central mean is 3.196, with a higher standard deviation of 7.65, suggesting that IC is highly volatile and requires further investigation. However, it has minimum and maximum means of 0 and 38.11, respectively, which means that some firms do not have intellectual capital recorded for them in certain year(s). In the same vein, HC averages 4.08, with a higher standard deviation of 6.647, suggesting that HC is highly volatile and therefore requires for further study. However, it has minimum and maximum means of 0 and 39.35, respectively, which means that some firms do not have human capital recorded for them in certain year(s). Furthermore, SC averages .017 points, with a higher standard deviation of .023 points, suggesting the volatility of SC, which requires further examination. However, it has minimum and maximum means of 0 and .08, respectively, which means that some firms do not have social capital recorded for them in certain year(s). In addition, MC averages 6.951 points, with a higher standard deviation of 8.47 points, suggesting the volatility of MC, which requires further examination. However, it has minimum and maximum means of .02 and 44.83, respectively. Also, NC averages 10.152 points, with a standard deviation of 8.534 points, suggesting that NC is not volatile. It has minimum and maximum means of .02 and 34.19, respectively.

On the auditors' characteristics, AO averages .033 points, with a higher standard deviation of .18 points, suggesting the volatility of AO, which requires further examination. However, it has minimum and maximum means of 0 and 1, respectively, suggesting that some firms, in some years do not qualify their opinion. Furthermore, AI averages 57.6 percent, with a lower standard deviation of 5.6 percent, suggesting that there is no volatility in AI. However, it has minimum and maximum means of 0 and 69.7 percent, respectively, meaning that some firms, in some year(s) have no record of audit fees as a proportion of total revenue. In addition, AFS averages 4.327 points, with a lower standard deviation of .437 points, suggesting non-volatility of AFS. However, it has minimum and maximum means of 2.683 points and 5.795 points, respectively. Furthermore, AT averages .694 years, with a lower standard deviation of .462 years, suggesting non-volatility of AT. However, it has minimum and maximum means of 0 and 1, respectively. In the same vein, AQ (big4) averages .878 points, with a lower standard deviation of .328 points, suggesting the non-volatility of AQ. However, it has minimum and maximum means of 0 and 1, respectively. Finally, AR averages .117 points, with a higher standard deviation of .322 points, suggesting the volatility of AR, which requires further examination. However, it has minimum and maximum means of 0 and 1, respectively.

We conduct series of diagnostic checks or tests, including normality of residuals, heteroskedasticity of residuals, multicollinearity test, and model specification error test. These tests were carried out in order to ensure that the models are best linear unbiased estimators (BLUE). We introduce the statistical linear model and identify the class of linear unbiased estimators.

We identify the best linear unbiased estimator for each model. The results of test of normality of residuals are in Table 2. The results of heteroskedasticity of residuals are in Table 3. Furthermore, the results of multicollinearity test are contained in Table 4a and Table 4b and the results of model specification error test are contained in Table 5.

Table 2

Results of normality of residuals

Source: STATA 16 Outputs

From the results in Table 2, it is visibly clear that IR model is not normally distributed. Therefore, the model requires robustness. Also, as indicated earlier, the results of heteroskedasticity of residuals are reported in Table 3.

Table 3

Results of heteroskedasticity of residuals

White's test for H_0 : homoskedasticity
 against H_a : unrestricted heteroskedasticity
 $\chi^2(38) = 93.76$
 $\text{Prob} > \chi^2 = 0.0000$

Cameron & Trivedi's decomposition of IM-test

Source	χ^2	Df	p
Heteroskedasticity	93.760	38	0.000
Skewness	20.270	8	0.009
Kurtosis	1.250	1	0.263
Total	115.280	47	0.000

Source: STATA 16 Outputs

Two results emerge from Table 3, one is the presence of heteroskedasticity and the second is the confirmation of non-normality of residuals. A normal distribution would have a skewness of 0 and Kurtosis of 3, since the Skewness and Kurtosis are outside acceptable values, Table 3 is a confirmation of the results in Table 2. In addition, the presence of heteroskedasticity in the model suggests that the model requires robustness. Table 4a reports the results of multicollinearity test. Table 4a

Results of multicollinearity test by correlation matrix

Variables	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)
(1) IR	1.000						
(2) AO	-0.142 (0.057)	1.000					
(3) AI	-0.034 (0.651)	0.116 (0.120)	1.000				
(4) AFS	-0.001 (0.988)	-0.310* (0.000)	0.232* (0.002)	1.000			
(5) AT	0.131 (0.080)	-0.213* (0.004)	-0.015 (0.844)	0.135 (0.071)	1.000		
(6) AQ	0.290* (0.000)	-0.309* (0.000)	-0.076 (0.310)	0.410* (0.000)	0.047 (0.531)	1.000	
(7) AR	-0.051 (0.498)	-0.067 (0.368)	0.036 (0.633)	0.072 (0.339)	-0.473* (0.000)	0.030 (0.690)	1.000

Source: STATA 16 Outputs

Pearson correlations reported in Table 4a do not exceed .410, which is lower than .80, which is the threshold of multicollinearity (Gujarati, 2005). The results in Table 4b contain variance inflation factors of independent and control variables for purpose of confirming the results in Table 4a.

Table 4b

Results of multicollinearity test by variance inflation factors

	VIF	1/VIF
AO	1.806	.554
AT	1.45	.689
AFS	1.439	.695
AR	1.364	.733
AQ	1.353	.739
AI	1.178	.849
Mean VIF	1.486	.

Source: STATA 16 Outputs

Also the variance inflation factor (VIF) values (calculated with every multiple regression model performed) not exceed 1.806. All VIF values are substantially below the critical value of 10.00 (Netter et al., 1989). Based on Pearson correlations (in Table 4a) and VIF values (in Table 4b), multicollinearity does not appear to be a concern or issue in this paper. In addition, we also conduct a model specification error test and results are reported in Table 5 as follows.

Table 5

Results of model specification error test

Source	SS	df	MS	Number of obs = 1,340		
Model	0.000	2	0.000	Prob>F = .000		
Residual	0.003	176	0.000	R-squared = .125		
Total	0.004	178	0.000	Root MSE = .004		

IR	Coef.	Std.Err.	T	P>t	[95% Con	Interval]
_hat	2.638	13.938	0.190	0.850	-24.870	30.146
_hatsq	-10.466	89.045	-0.120	0.907	-186.200	165.268
_cons	-0.064	0.545	-0.120	0.907	-1.140	1.012

Source: STATA 16 Outputs

Furthermore, the results in Table 5 show that the p-value of _hatsq is .907, which is higher than the threshold of .05, suggesting that there is no model specification error. Thus, both the original 2 control variables were dropped. Also, the core research question in this paper is to assess whether auditors' characteristics lead to higher or lower integrated reporting by corporations in Nigeria. Table 6 reports regression analysis results based on the Generalised Method of Moments (GMM) for Model 1. The GMM model, which is generally used for panel data, provides consistent results in the presence of different sources of endogeneity (Wintoki et al., 2012).

Table 6

Results of GMM Regression Analysis (IR)

	Coefficients	Robust standard error	z	p/z/	95% confidence	Interval
/xb_AO	-.0015443	.0013742	-1.12	0.261	-.0042377	.0011491
/xb_AI	-.0027361	.0086847	-0.32	0.753	-.0197578	.0142856
/xb_AFS	-.001809	.0009371	-1.93	0.054	-.0036457	.0000277
/xb_AT	.0013296	.0006868	1.94	0.053	-.0000164	.0026757
/xb_AQ	.0046959	.0008826	5.32	0.000	.0029661	.0064257
/xb_AR	.0001354	.0006575	0.21	0.837	-.0011533	.001424
/b0	.0837428	.0049685	16.85	0.000	.0740046	.0934809

Number of parameters = 7

Number of moments = 7

Initial weight matrix: Unadjusted

Number of obs = 1,340

GMM weight matrix: Robust

Source: STATA 16 Outputs

From the results in Table 6, there are two (2) broad results; auditors' opinion, auditors' independence and auditors rotation are not significant. However, in contrast, audit firm size, auditors' tenure and audit quality (big4) have significant effects on IR. While, audit firm size and auditors' tenure are significant at 10 percent, audit quality is significant at 1 percent. Overall, these results are mixed, which are consistent with empirical literature. Furthermore, we also talk about determining the effect of auditors; characteristics on each component parts of IR and the GMM regression results are presented in Tables 7 to 12 as follows.

Table 7

Results of GMM Regression Analysis (HC)

	Coefficients	Robust standard error	z	p/z/	95% confidence	Interval
/xb_AO	16.13845	5.233527	3.08	0.002	5.880925	26.39597
/xb_AI	-14.17302	11.81071	-1.20	0.230	-37.32158	8.97555
/xb_AFS	-1.664025	1.396518	-1.19	0.233	-4.401149	1.0731
/xb_AT	2.454938	.7987931	3.07	0.002	.8893321	4.020543
/xb_AQ	-3.859237	2.335027	-1.65	0.098	-8.435805	.7173323
/xb_AR	.903776	.8438294	1.07	0.284	-.7500992	2.557651
/b0	20.53438	6.024032	3.41	0.001	8.72749	32.34126

Number of parameters = 7

Number of moments = 7

Initial weight matrix: Unadjusted

Number of obs = 1,340

GMM weight matrix: Robust

Source: STATA 16 Outputs

As indicated by the results in Table 7, when IR is replaced by HC, both auditors opinion, auditors' tenure and audit quality (big4) show significant effects on HC. Although, while both auditors' opinion and auditors' tenure are significant at 1 percent, audit quality is significant at 10 percent. However, in contrast, both auditors' independence, audit firm size and auditors' rotation show no sign of significance at all. In the same manner, when IR is replaced by FC, the results are reported in Table 8 as follows.

Table 8

Results of GMM Regression Analysis (FC)

	Coefficients	Robust standard error	z	p/z/	95% confidence	Interval
/xb_AO	52.15158	26.79623	1.95	0.052	-.3680624	104.6712
/xb_AI	-1.158058	41.20524	-0.03	0.978	-81.91884	79.60273
/xb_AFS	.7624265	5.186787	0.15	0.883	-9.40349	10.92834
/xb_AT	2.157354	3.29642	0.65	0.513	-4.303511	8.618219
/xb_AQ	-11.72431	8.967946	-1.31	0.191	-29.30117	5.852536
/xb_AR	.8612993	3.235281	0.27	0.790	-5.479734	7.202333
/b0	76.60612	23.90687	3.20	0.001	29.74952	123.4627

Number of parameters = 7

Number of moments = 7

Initial weight matrix: Unadjusted

Number of obs = 1,340

GMM weight matrix: Robust

Source: STATA 16 Outputs

As indicated by the results in Table 8, when IR is replaced by FC, only auditors opinion show significant effect. Although, auditors' opinion is significant at 10 percent, the remaining five auditors' characteristics are not significant at all. In the same manner, when IR is replaced by IC, the results are reported in Table 9 as follows.

Table 9

Results of GMM Regression Analysis (IC)

	Coefficients	Robust standard error	z	p/z/	95% confidence	Interval
/xb_AO	9.128083	5.258658	1.74	0.083	-1.178696	19.43486
/xb_AI	-4.17721	14.85098	-0.28	0.778	-33.28459	24.93017
/xb_AFS	-1.068251	1.398678	-0.76	0.445	-3.809609	1.673108
/xb_AT	.6285945	1.124317	0.56	0.576	-1.575027	2.832216
/xb_AQ	-7.581319	2.452537	-3.09	0.002	-12.3882	-2.774435
/xb_AR	1.582332	2.002874	0.79	0.430	-2.343228	5.507892
/b0	15.97634	4.770162	3.35	0.001	6.626996	25.32569

Number of parameters = 7

Number of moments = 7

Initial weight matrix: Unadjusted

Number of obs = 1,340

GMM weight matrix: Robust

Source: STATA 16 Outputs

As indicated by the results in Table 9, when IR is replaced by IC, only auditors opinion and audit quality (big4) show significant effect. Although, auditors' opinion is significant at 10 percent while audit quality is significant at 1 percent, the remaining four auditors' characteristics are not significant at all. In the same manner, when IR is replaced by SC, the results are reported in Table 10 as follows.

Table 10

Results of GMM Regression Analysis (SC)

	Coefficients	Robust standard error	z	p/z/	95% confidence	Interval
/xb_AO	-.0081924	.0038098	-2.15	0.032	-.0156596	-.0007252
/xb_AI	.0340337	.0430107	0.79	0.429	-.0502657	.1183331
/xb_AFS	-.0160415	.0049984	-3.21	0.001	-.0258383	-.0062447
/xb_AT	.0019845	.0038774	0.51	0.609	-.005615	.009584
/xb_AQ	.0234213	.003527	6.64	0.000	.0165086	.0303341
/xb_AR	-.007188	.0045215	-1.59	0.112	-.01605	.001674
/b0	.0453912	.0295428	1.54	0.124	-.0125117	.1032941

Number of parameters = 7

Number of moments = 7

Initial weight matrix: Unadjusted

Number of obs = 1,340

GMM weight matrix: Robust

Source: STATA 16 Outputs

As indicated by the results in Table 10, when IR is replaced by SC, auditors' opinion, audit firm size and audit quality show significant effect. Although, auditors' opinion is significant at 5 percent, audit firm size and audit quality are significant at 1 percent. The remaining three auditors' characteristics are not significant at all. In the same manner, when IR is replaced by MC, the results are reported in Table 11 as follows.

Table 11

Results of GMM Regression Analysis (MC)

	Coefficients	Robust standard error	z	p/z/	95% confidence	Interval
/xb_AO	-5.448889	2.145072	-2.54	0.011	-9.653153	-1.244626
/xb_AI	-1.083173	18.97896	-0.06	0.954	-38.28125	36.1149
/xb_AFS	-.9584215	1.425004	-0.67	0.501	-3.751377	1.834534
/xb_AT	.6370711	1.852621	0.34	0.731	-2.993999	4.268141
/xb_AQ	-.4836926	1.346463	-0.36	0.719	-3.122711	2.155326
/xb_AR	4.586502	3.672505	1.25	0.212	-2.611476	11.78448
/b0	11.39531	9.38706	1.21	0.225	-7.002984	29.79361

Number of parameters = 7

Number of moments = 7

Initial weight matrix: Unadjusted

Number of obs = 1,340

GMM weight matrix: Robust

Source: STATA 16 Outputs

As indicated by the results in Table 11, when IR is replaced by MC, only auditors' opinion show significant effect. Although, auditors' opinion is significant at 5 percent, the remaining five auditors' characteristics are not significant at all. Finally, when IR is replaced by NC, the results are reported in Table 12 as follows.

Table 12

Results of GMM Regression Analysis (NC)

	Coefficients	Robust standard error	z	p/z/	95% confidence	Interval
/xb_AO	-4.186789	2.200843	-1.90	0.057	-8.500362	.1267837
/xb_AI	11.63248	17.09107	0.68	0.496	-21.8654	45.13037
/xb_AFS	1.275836	1.565625	0.81	0.415	-1.792732	4.344405
/xb_AT	-3.29044	1.753653	-1.88	0.061	-6.727537	.1466575
/xb_AQ	-9.334847	1.524818	-6.12	0.000	-12.32343	-6.346259
/xb_AR	-.4635583	2.682392	-0.17	0.863	-5.720949	4.793833
/b0	8.601675	10.56384	0.81	0.415	-12.10306	29.30641

Number of parameters = 7

Number of moments = 7

Initial weight matrix: Unadjusted

Number of obs = 1,340

GMM weight matrix: Robust

Source: STATA 16 Outputs

As indicated by the results in Table 12, when IR is replaced by NC, auditors' opinion, auditors' tenure and audit quality show significant effect. Although, both auditors' opinion and auditors' tenure are significant at 10 percent, audit quality show significance at 1 percent. The remaining three auditors' characteristics are not significant at all. The remaining section is on conclusions and recommendations.

Conclusions and Recommendations

We examine whether auditors' characteristics improve integrated reporting by firms in Nigeria, if so, which part of integrated reporting have greater influence. We observe that audit firm size and auditors' tenure show significance at 10 percent. Audit quality (big4) shows significance at 1 percent. The remaining three auditors' characteristics (auditors' opinion, auditors' independence and auditors' rotation) failed to show any level of significance at all. Thus, we conclude that audit firm size, auditors' tenure and audit quality are determinants of integrated reporting among the 134 main board founding firms in Nigeria. However, we also conclude that we fail to see results for auditors' opinion, auditors' independence and auditors' rotation. These results are of obvious interest to regulators, shareholders, publics, lenders, scholars, policy-makers, as corporations managers should move closer to embracing integrated reporting.

Regulators should insist that external auditors play a major role in ensuring that their clients use integrated reporting framework, designed to increase reports about their clients. The reform of audit and assurance functions should focus on strengthening the reporting system for both financial and non-financial information. One of the recommendations is on the appointment of audit firms, a consideration for one of the big4 is an obvious consideration for boards of directors or their audit committee. Furthermore, managers should consider audit firm size in appointment of auditors. Another important recommendation is the tenure of external auditors; it must be taken into consideration in the appointment of external auditors because it shows that it is a determinant. The findings of this study contribute to the existing literature concerning IR adoption. These findings can be useful to regulators, as the authors provide some evidence regarding the effectiveness of the role of external auditors in IR adoption. The remainder of the paper consists of references.

Note that this study suffers from some limitations. First, the study sample is limited to only 1,340 observations. However, this is due to the number of listed main board founding firms and to the small number of listed firms on the Nigerian Exchange. Second, the study period begins in 2013 and ended in 2022, which last for 10 years only. Third, although this study examines the effect of auditors' characteristics, not all the auditors' features have been examined in our models. Future research may consider other auditors' characteristics such as joint auditor, auditor specialization, audit fee, audit report delay, auditors' busyness, auditors' international affiliation, and auditors' restatement. Nonetheless, this research is pioneering in analysing the effects of auditors' characteristics on integrated reporting and as far as we know no existing research has examined the link between them.

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